

ASSESSING THE IMPACTS OF CAPACITY BUILDING ON TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KWARA STATE

BY

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Abstract

This study examined the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Kwara State. It adopted descriptive research design of survey type. One research question was raised while two hypotheses were formulated in the study. Eight thousand five hundred and sixty-three teachers formed population of the study. Six Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected. A proportionate sampling technique was used to select 60 public senior secondary schools out of the 181 in the sampled LGAs while 354 teachers were proportionately selected out the 4,750 in the sampled LGAs. The Impacts of Capacity Building on Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (ICBTJQ) was used for data collection. The research question was answered using mean and standard deviation, while the t-test and Analysis of Variance were used to test hypotheses. The instrument was validated, tested for reliability through the use of Chronbach's Alpha and reliability index of 0.85 was realized. The study found that capacity building helps to increase the horizon of teachers' knowledge in their respective areas of specialization, increase teachers' proficiency in student assessment and assist teachers to acquire knowledge on how to handle emerging techniques for imparting knowledge to students. It recommended that government should be more committed to the capacity building programmes through conferences, seminars, lectures, and seminars are periodically organized for teachers, to update enhance their job performance.

Keywords: Capacity, Building, Job, Performance, Teachers, Gender, Years of Experience

Introduction

The position of teachers in education system is a sensitive one because they are the tripod upon which all other resources rest on to achieve the set goals. If teachers are up-and-coming in the aspects of knowledge acquisition in their respective subjects, and possess the skills and techniques for the conveyance of information to students, it could assist achieving the established goals. However, capacity building is required for teachers to have updated knowledge, techniques, and skills which they need to operate effectively.

As opined by Gbaeprekmo et al. (2024), capacity building could take place on a societal, institutional, and individual level. It involves setting favourable circumstances that enable employees to improve and

expand on their current knowledge and abilities, and eventually enhance the goal achievement of the organization. Maxwell (2024) believed that capacity building means the process of increasing the proficiency and potential of employees in an organization, to achieve the set goals effectively. Furthermore, capacity building means an intentional and well-planned process of crafting, consolidating, and retaining the potentials of workers to actualise the stated objectives. Chan et al. (2021) elucidated capacity building as the act of consolidating the capabilities of workers, to be able to discharge their fundamental responsibilities and continue to advance and improve over time. Kukawa et al. (2024) explained capacity building as the incessant development process of teachers' abilities in their careers until retirement. Smyth (2022)

viewed capacity building as the improvement and development of the capabilities, competencies and capabilities required for effective service delivery of employees in their respective places of work.

Teachers are employed in schools for the purpose of performing specific jobs to enhance goal achievement. Ismail et al. (2020) posited that job performance is the extent of contribution which an employee makes towards the attainment of the organizational goals. An employee's job performance is measured by comparing it with the organizational set goals. Sulyman et al. (2024) elucidated job performance as the manner in which teachers discharge their statutory services apportioned to them such as classroom management, lesson presentation, student assessment, lesson plan preparation and records keeping. Ogunode (2023) stated that the extent to which educators successfully carry out their designated tasks and responsibilities in schools can be used to gauge their job performance. Uko et al. (2015) stressed that teachers' job performance means the level of dedication which teachers exhibit to successful pedagogical implementation, together with their honesty and academic prowess. In addition, job performance means the duties which are designed for teachers to carry out as professionals. These include, student evaluation, instructional delivery, record keeping, classroom management, and lesson plan preparation, among others.

The importance of capacity building to teachers' job performance cannot be underrated. Wey-Ameawhule and Dikeogu (2023) maintained that through exposure of teachers to various capacity building programmes, the quality of teaching which they impart to students is improved. Capacity building allows teachers to have access to the needed knowledge and skills in the teaching and learning process. Osamwonyi (2016)

believed that via capacity building such as in-service training, workshops, conferences, and seminars, teachers acquire new, skills, techniques, and methods which eventually have positive impact on their instructional delivery. Obiye (2019) maintained that capacity building of teachers is significant to the effective functioning of education as well as other sectors of the economy. This is because all other sectors depend on education and teachers drive education to develop other sectors and enhance national development. Wey-Ameawhule and Dikeogu (2023) submitted that capacity building programs, such as workshops and in-service training assist in enhancing teachers' job performance.

The effectiveness of job performance of teachers could increase when they are periodically encouraged by giving them the chance to participate in various trainings via capacity building. Kukawa et al. (2024) believed that for teachers to perform their jobs well, they have to acquire the necessary knowledge and abilities. This makes capacity building of teachers a necessity. Wey-Ameawhule and Dikeogu (2023) posited that capacity building is a powerful method for expanding teachers' knowledge and abilities is capacity building, which helps them learn new concepts and stay current on emerging challenges. The knowledge-intensive, skill-acquisition economy of the twenty-first century demands that educators possess the abilities necessary for problem solving and this can only be achieved via capacity building.

The study conducted by Kukawa et al. (2024) revealed that significant improvement existed in the job performance of teachers who participated in the capacity building interventions. Those who participated performed better than the control group that did not participate. Bolaji (2018) found in his study that there was no significant difference

in the opinions of teachers on the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in basic schools in Lagos State based on gender. The findings of Olawepo (2020) revealed that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female teachers on the influence of capacity building on teachers' job performance in basic schools in Idanre Local Government, Ondo State. As revealed by the findings of Noah (2017), a significant difference did not exist in the opinions of male and female teachers on the effect of professional development on job performance of teachers in junior secondary schools in Ijumu Local Government, Kogi State. The outcome of the study conducted by Lamidi (2021) found that there was no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in basic schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria based on years of experience. The findings of the study of Bolaji (2018) found that there was no significant difference in the opinions of teachers on the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in basic schools in Lagos State based on years of experience.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching is a dynamic profession which involves updating the knowledge, skills, and techniques of teachers from time to time, to make their job performance effective. However, it is not palatable that job performance of some teachers in public secondary schools in Kwara State seems ineffective. Conferences, workshops, lectures, symposia, and seminars need to be organized for teachers periodically to assist them boosting their knowledge, skills and techniques. Unfortunately, the attention given to capacity building by teachers seems inadequate, as gathered from some teachers, principals and members of the public; hence, ineffective instructional delivery, classroom management, lesson plan preparation, ability

to improvise and use instructional materials and the likes.

Many researchers have conducted various studies related to this study. For instance, Sulyman et al. (2024) conducted a comparative analysis of teachers' job performance in private and public secondary schools' quality in Ilorin East Local Government Area, Kwara State. Uko et al. (2015) examined administrators' resource management practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Eket Education Zone of Akwa-Ibom State, Nigeria. Wey-Ameawhule and Dikeogu (2023) conducted a study on the influence of capacity building programmes on teachers' job productivity in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Noah (2017) researched the effect of professional development on job performance of teachers in junior secondary schools in Ijumu Local Government, Kogi State. However, no research, out of the ones identified above, assessed the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Kwara State. This was the observed gap which the study targeted at filling.

Purpose of the Study

The study specific purposes of the study include:

1. Investigated the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Kwara State.
2. Examined the difference in the impact of capacity building on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Kwara State, based on gender.
3. Determined the difference in the impact of capacity building on teachers' job performance in senior

secondary schools in Kwara State, based on years of experience.

Research Questions

1. What are the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools, Kwara State?
2. Is there difference in the impact of capacity building on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Kwara State, based on years of gender?
3. Is there difference in the impact of capacity building on teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Kwara State, based on years of experience?

Null Hypotheses

- Ho1: There is no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Kwara State based on gender.
- Ho1: There is no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Kwara State based on years of experience.

Research Methods

The study adopted a descriptive research design of survey type. Eight thousand five hundred and sixty-three teachers in the public secondary schools in the state formed population of the study. The study used a multi-stage sampling technique. Random sampling technique was used to select two Local Government Areas (LGAs) from each of the three senatorial districts, that is, Ilorin West and Ilorin East from Kwara Central, Irepodun and Oyun from Kwara South, and Patigi and Edu from Kwara North. This formed six (37.5%) LGAs out of the 18 in

the state. Sixty schools (13 out of the 39 in Ilorin West and 11 out of the 33 in Ilorin East; 6 out of the 17 in Patigi and nine out of the 28 in Edu; and 14 out of the 43 in Irepodun and 7 out of the 21 in Oyun) were proportionately sampled out of the 181 in the LGAs, representing 33.3% of the school population. Three hundred and fifty-four teachers (163 out of the 2,181 in Ilorin West, 76 out of the 1,023 in Ilorin East, 38 out of the 512 in Edu, 13 out of the 172 in Patigi Local, 25 out of the 336 in Oyun and 39 out of the 526 in Irepodun) were proportionately sampled, using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample size determination.

Data collection was carried out via the use of the Impacts of Capacity Building on Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (ICBTJPQ). The instrument had 10 items with rating scale of Strongly Agree rated 4, Agree scored 3, Disagree assigned 2 and Strongly Disagree given 1. It was also divided into two sections (A and B). Section A focused on the demographic information of the respondents while Section B contained items which addressed the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance. The researchers used three experts in the field of Educational Management to validate the questionnaire. Twenty five copies of the instrument were administered to some teachers out of the sample of the study, Cronbach's Alpha was used to analyse the data and reliability index of 0.85 was realized. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question, while t-test and Analysis of variance were used to test hypotheses one and two respectively. Setting the benchmark for making decisions, any mean score between 1.00 and 2.49 was considered 'Disagree' while any score found between 2.50 and 4.00 was adjudged 'Agree'. Out of the 354 copies of the questionnaire distributed, only 321 (90.7%) copies properly

filled out and received from the respondents were used for analysis.

Results

What are the impacts of capacity building on teachers’ job performance in senior secondary schools, Kwara State?

Table 1 Impacts of Capacity Building on Teachers’ Job Performance in Secondary Schools, Kwara State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Capacity building helps to: increase the frontier of teachers’ knowledge in the improvisation of instructional materials	3.31	1.11	Agree
2.	increase the horizon of teachers’ knowledge in their respective areas of specialisation	3.10	.98	Agree
3.	assist teachers in acquiring knowledge on how to handle emerging techniques for imparting knowledge to students	3.24	1.20	Agree
4.	expose teachers to various methods of assessing students	3.17	.85	Agree
5.	make teachers accustomed to the use of information communication technology for effective instructional delivery	2.94	.71	Agree
6.	enhance cross-fertilisation of ideas among teachers their improve their service delivery	3.52	1.36	Agree
7.	increase teachers’ proficiency in student assessment	3.42	1.29	Agree
8.	enhance teachers’ skills in the preparation of a comprehensive lesson plan	3.01	.93	Agree
9.	boost teachers’ confidence in instructional delivery	3.55	1.22	Agree
10.	improve teachers’ skills in classroom management	3.61	1.31	Agree

Table 1 shows the impacts of capacity building on teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State, As shown on the table 1, items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 (increase the frontier of teachers’ knowledge in the improvisation and of instructional materials, increase the horizon of teachers’ knowledge in their respective areas of specialization, assist teachers to acquire knowledge on how to handle emerging techniques for imparting knowledge to students, expose teachers to various methods of assessing students and

make teachers accustomed to the use of information communication technology for effective instructional delivery) had mean scores of 3.31, 3.10, 3.24, 3.17 and 2.94 respectively; hence the decision taken on them was ‘Agree’. Furthermore, items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 (enhance cross-fertilization of ideas among teachers their improve service delivery, increase teachers’ proficiency in student assessment, enhance teachers’ skills in the preparation of comprehensive lesson plan, boost teachers’ confidence in instructional delivery and improve teachers’

skills in classroom management) had mean scores of 3.52, 3.42, 3.01, 3.55 and 3.61; therefore, the decision on them was agree.

Testing Null Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Kwara State based on gender

Table 2 Impacts of Capacity Building on Teachers’ Job Performance Based on Gender

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	126	3.43	1.01	2.43	.052	Ho ₁ Accepted
Female	195	3.15	1.19			

Table 2 shows the calculated t-value (2.43), a mean difference of 0.28 and the p-value (0.71) which is greater than 0.05, which is the level of significance. As a result of this, the decision taken, null hypothesis one was accepted. This means that a significant difference did not exist in the impacts of

capacity building on teachers’ job performance based on gender.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers’ job Performance in secondary schools in Kwara State based on years of experience.

Table 3 Impacts of Capacity Building on Teachers’ Job Performance Based on Years of Experience.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	Cal. F-ratio	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	13.119	3	.312	2.20	.064	Ho ₂ Accepted
Within Groups	16.642	318	.174			
Total	29.761	321				

Table 3 shows the cal. F-ratio (2.20) and the p-value (.064) that is greater than 0.05 which is the level of significance. Therefore, the decision taken on the null hypothesis two

(Ho2) was ‘accepted’. This depicts that there was no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers’ job performance based on years of experience knowledge to students, expose teachers to various methods of assessing students and make teachers accustomed to the use of information communication technology for effective instructional delivery, enhance cross-fertilization of ideas among teachers improve their service delivery, increase teachers’ proficiency in student assessment, enhance teachers’ skills in the preparation of comprehensive lesson plan, boost teachers’

.Discussions

The findings of the study showed that capacity building helps to increase the frontier of teachers’ knowledge in the improvisation and of instructional materials, increase the horizon of teachers’ knowledge in their respective areas of specialization, assist teachers to acquire knowledge on how to handle emerging techniques for imparting

confidence in instructional delivery and improve teachers' skills in classroom management. The finding corroborates the finding of Olawepo (2020) which revealed that capacity building assists in boosting teachers' knowledge in classroom management, instructional delivery, knowledge of subject matter, lesson plan preparation and student evaluation. The finding agrees with the finding of Obiye (2019) that capacity building improves teachers' job effectiveness and has a significant influence on the academic performance of students. The finding is also in tandem with the finding of Wey-Ameawhule and Dikeogu (2023) which revealed that capacity building such as in-service training, training on ICT and workshops had a significant influence on teachers' job productivity.

The findings of the study showed that there was no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance based on gender. This finding confirms the finding of Olawepo (2020) which showed that male and female teachers were not significantly different in their opinions on the influence of capacity building on teachers' job performance in basic schools based on gender. The finding also agrees with the finding of Noah (2017) which showed that there was no significant difference in the impacts of professional development on job performance of teachers based on gender.

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance based on years of experience. This finding aligns with the finding of Lamidi (2021) which revealed that there was no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in basic schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. This finding supports the finding of

Bolaji (2018) which found that there was no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance in basic schools in Lagos State based on years of experience.

Conclusion

The study concluded that capacity building helps to increase the horizon of teachers' knowledge in their respective areas of specialization, increase teachers' proficiency in student assessment, assist teachers to acquire knowledge on how to handle emerging techniques for imparting knowledge to students, increase the frontier of teachers' knowledge in the improvisation and of instructional materials, enhance teachers' skills in the preparation of comprehensive lesson plan, boost teachers' confidence in instructional delivery and improve teachers' skills in classroom management and expose teachers to various methods of assessing students, enhance cross-fertilization of ideas among teachers their improve their services delivery and make teachers accustomed to the use of information communication technology for effective instructional delivery. Also, there was no significant difference in the impacts of capacity building on teachers' job performance based on gender and years of experience.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- i. It recommended that government should be more committed to the capacity building programmes through conferences, seminars, lectures, and seminars are periodically organized for teachers, to update enhance their job performance.

- ii. School principals should also be committed to using their rich professional experience to benefit teachers in their schools, to boost their knowledge and facilitate their effective job performance.
- iii. Teachers should always show a high level of seriousness in any capacity building programme for them to derive adequate benefits from it and eventually enhance their job performance.

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